

IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL THINKING OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS BASED ON THE PEDAGOGICAL VIEWS OF EASTERN STUDENTS

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Abstract: the article reflects the views of Eastern scientists on improving the pedagogical thinking of students of higher educational institutions based on the literary heritage of Abu Hasr Farabi, Al-Khorezmi, Beruni and Ibn Sina.

Key words: pedagogical thinking, teaching, learning, professional experience, Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorezmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Raihan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina.

INTRODUCTION

Pedagogical thinking is a generalized reflection and creative modification of the objective features of the pedagogical process, features of pedagogical phenomena, goals and objectives of teaching and upbringing, as well as modeling of the processes of teaching and upbringing, determined by professional experience. One of the ways to improve the pedagogical thinking of university students is the effective use of the pedagogical views of Eastern scientists in the system of taught subjects. Among the scientists of the East, our great ancestors, such as Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorezmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, with their scientific and creative heritage not only contributed to the knowledge of their people, but also to the high level of science throughout the world who conquered the peaks.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: “If we look at history, we will see that our Motherland, located at the intersection of the Great Silk Road, has been one of

the centers of high civilization and culture since time immemorial. The rich scientific and cultural heritage of our people, ancient stone inscriptions, priceless architectural monuments, rare manuscripts, and various antiques testify to the deep roots of the three-thousand-year history of our statehood.

The famous orientalist J. Sarton called the first half of the 11th century Beruni a period in the history of world science. He was considered the first world sage of his time. Famous scientist S.P. Tolstov dedicated his monograph “In the Footsteps of the Ancient Khorezmian Civilization” to Abu Rayhan al-Beruni from Khorezm.

Academician V. R. Rosen evaluates Beruni’s work “India” as “there is no work equal to it among all the scientific literature of the East and West in antiquity and the Middle Ages.”

Indian scholar Hamid Reza, speaking about the scholar Beruni, said: “No medieval or modern author could so successfully understand the complex problems of Indian culture as Abu Rayhan Beruni.”

S. P. Tolstov, A. A. Freiman, M. Aripov on the history of education. O'.Aleuov, Kh.Boboiev, A.Zunnunov, B.Kadirov, S.Nishonova, Kh.Tillashev. K. Khoshimov. O. Gasanboeva, J. Gasanboev. Human perfection of encyclopedist scientists, features of pedagogical phenomena, goals of teaching and education in the research of Z. Nuritdinova, E. Torakulov, S. Ragimov, Kh. Khomidov, K. Nosirov, F. Babazhev, N. Makhmudova and tasks, as well as their opinions on issues of modeling educational processes, determined by professional experience, in modern language.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article discusses the pedagogical views of Eastern scientists on improving the pedagogical thinking of university students. The pedagogical views of Eastern scientists are described. The pedagogical views of Eastern scientists are analyzed and these approaches are studied.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The encyclopedist Allama Muhammad al-Khorezmi synthesized the basic ideas, principles and methods of scientific knowledge of his time. He paid attention to students' independent acquisition of scientific knowledge. Khorezmi paid great attention to the student's personal observations and the use of acquired knowledge. In doing so, he highly valued the skills and abilities of those who seek knowledge to gather scientific sources, express them, and explain what they observed. For example, in the work "Al-kitab al-mukhtasar fi lishb al-jabr wal-l muqabala," he divides scholars into three groups: He can bequeath it to his successors. The other interprets the works of her predecessors and thereby alleviates difficulties. , opens what is closed, illuminates the path and makes it more understandable. Or he is a person who finds fault in some books and collects scattered ones, he has a good opinion of those who came before him, he is not arrogant and is not proud of what he has done. The encyclopedist Abu Nasr Farabi expressed his opinion on the procedure for acquiring knowledge in his work "Happiness - about achieving happiness." He stated that the first thing to study is the science that needs to be known, this is the science of the foundations of the universe. After studying it, it is necessary to study the natural sciences, the structure and shape of natural bodies, and knowledge about the sky. After this, the science of living nature, plants and animals is mainly studied. Farabi says that a person cannot achieve perfection on his own. He needs to be in contact with other people, their help or relationships. In his opinion, it is important that the educational process is organized by an experienced teacher and educator. Because not everyone can experience happiness and events on their own. For this he needs a teacher. Farabi says this can be achieved through proper education. Because purposeful upbringing and training makes a person perfect both intellectually and morally, in particular, a person correctly assimilates the laws of nature and society and leads the right way

of life, behaves correctly with others, and follows the rules of society. Therefore, Farabi believes that the main task of education is to educate a mature person capable of satisfying the needs of society and serving this society. Beruni, an encyclopedist, considers man to be the highest perfection of nature. He divides all moral qualities of a person's mental image into 2 types: good and bad. Reflecting on human and moral education, Beruni says: "Man is given reason to improve the earth and manage it, therefore every person must have high morals." Intellectual education, says Beruni, develops a person's thinking, expands his worldview, and develops a range of thinking. This affects his sense of self. As can be seen from the above, Beruni's ideas about the formation of a perfect person are of great importance not only for his time, but also for improving modern education. After all, he proved that he possesses truly perfect human qualities, left a great spiritual legacy for future generations, proved this with his life, creativity and works. Beruni became famous as one of the encyclopedist scientists of the Eastern Renaissance.

The encyclopedist Abu Ali ibn Sina at one time paid serious attention to the issue of classification of sciences and wrote a work in this area entitled "Aksam al-ulum alakliyya" ("Classification of intellectual sciences"). The scientist of "Aqşam al-Uloom Alakliya" perceives intellectual sciences as hikmat - philosophical sciences and divides them into theoretical and practical parts. Theoretical sciences are aimed at knowing the truth, applied sciences are aimed at doing good deeds.

Theoretical philosophy is divided into 3:

- 1) lower-level sciences, i.e. natural sciences (medicine, chemistry, astrology, etc.);
- 2) intermediate level science – math. (geometry, arithmetic, astronomy, music);
- 3) science of the highest level - metaphysics (theology).

Practical philosophy consists of three parts:

- 1) morality. This part describes thoughts about one person and what his character will be like.
- 2) economics. This part shows how people relate to each other in family and household matters.
- 3) divided into policies.

This part talks about how people interact with each other on a city or country scale and how to govern the state. These categories are also divided into smaller industries. The work mentions the branch of science, Ibn Sina argues that true moral qualities and an ideal community can be achieved in this existing world, and people should live in a society based on mutual support. It states that society should be governed by fair laws adopted by mutual consent of people. All members of society must obey this law, violation of the law and injustice must be punished. He believes that if the ruler himself commits injustice, then the uprising of the people against him is correct and should be supported by society. In his reflections on morality, he pays special attention to the most necessary moral relations in the everyday activities of people, moral rules, such as modesty, honor, courage, correctness, and honesty.

Ibn Sina, with his rich and rich scientific heritage, had a great influence on the development of Eastern and Western culture in the subsequent period.

Show future teachers that the experience of using the pedagogical views of Eastern scientists in improving the pedagogical thinking of university students is a logical continuation of the organic development of pedagogical thinking and will help to understand education and training in the future. The main goal is to bring to the consciousness of young people the educational and moral views of the great thinkers Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina. It is expected to carry out work on organizing the educational process based on the ideas of Eastern thinkers about pedagogical thinking, that is, about education and intelligence. In this regard, it

is expected to reveal that Eastern thinkers, when cultivating the spiritual qualities of a perfect person and studying the history of mankind, took into account the intellectual, civil, spiritual and moral, physical, hardworking, economic, environmental, and aesthetic aspects. pedagogy, education, content, forms and styles, tools of these components.

CONCLUSION

Purely pedagogical works were created during the Eastern Renaissance, and the scientific creations of scientist-teachers, who left a name with their immortal teaching about special and general methods of human development in education, retain their value to this day. The ideas and views of lexicographers on education also impressed European scientists.

References.

1. Xamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "EVACUATION OF THE LEVEL OF CONFLICTS IN CONFLICT SITUATIONS BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS." *Confrencea* 1.1 (2023): 23-27.
<https://confrencea.org/index.php/confrenceas/article/view/372/375>
2. Khamidovna, Mamayusupova Iroda. "MASTERY OF MANAGING PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION STUDY, GENERALIZATION AND DISSEMINATION OF ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 1217-1222.
<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/4627/4322>
3. Khamidovna M. I. CAUSES OF FAMILY CONFLICTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 12. – C. 870-872.
<https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3156/2907>
4. Goziev E. *Psychology of secondary school*. T: 1997.

5. General psychology. Edited by A. V. Petrovsky. T: 1992
6. Davletshin M.G. Development of technical abilities in sleepers. T: 1991 1.
4. Barysheva T.A., Zhigalov Yu.A. Psychological and pedagogical fundamentals of developing creativity - St. Petersburg: SPGUTD, 2006.
7. Bashina T.F., Ilyin E.P. Psychology of creativity, creativity, creativity. - KPb.: Peter, 2009.
8. Mukhiddinov A.G. Speech activity in the educational process. – T.: Teacher, 1995.
9. Saidakhmedov N. Pedagogical skills and pedagogical technology. - T.: OPI, 2003.
10. Sultonova G.A. Teaching skills. - T.: TDPU im. Nizami, 2005.
11. Gudratov T. Fundamentals of speech culture / Textbook on OO'Yu. - T.: “Teacher”, 1993.